

for analytical work to keep CHCl_3 content of solutions to a minimum ($\leq 5\%$ v/v).

Results and Discussion

Absorption Spectra: Spectral curve of the reagent at pH 3.0 shows two maxima at 330 nm and 400-410 nm respectively. The curve for the Ni(II) complex at pH 3.0 against reagent blank exhibits two peaks at 380 nm ($\epsilon = 3350$) and 505 nm ($\epsilon = 2760$) respectively. The latter wavelength has been chosen for analytical work and appropriate reagent blanks were used for absorption measurements on the complex as the reagent has some absorption at this wavelength.

Effect of pH: Spectral curves of the Ni(II) complex at different pH in the acidic medium are very similar in the pH region 2.0-4.1, in which the same complex species is presumably formed. The absorbance at 505 nm is maximum and constant in the pH region 2.0-3.5.

Stability of the Colour: Development of the full colour intensity of the complex is complete within 20 min and the absorbance is not significantly changed up to at least 4 hr. Absorbance is constant in the temperature range 10-45°.

Procedure for the Determination of Nickel: To a suitable aliquot (≤ 2 ml) of an acidic sample solution containing 5-100 μg of nickel, add 0.5 ml of thio-salen solution in CHCl_3 , followed by sufficient acetone and make up to 10.0 ml, adjusting the pH to 3.0 ± 0.5 , and keeping the acetone content at 75% (v/v). Mix and keep for 20 min. Measure the absorbance at 505 nm against a reagent blank prepared in the same way but without Ni(II) solution.

Beer's Law, Sensitivity, Precision and Accuracy: The purple coloured Ni(II) complex adheres to Beer's law in the range 0.5-10.0 μg of Ni(II)/ml. The molar absorptivity is 2.76×10^4 at 505 nm and the Sandell sensitivity of the method is 0.02 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. The precision and accuracy of the method tested by analysing samples containing 4.0 μg of Ni(II)/ml, gave the average of ten determinations as 4.00 ± 0.05 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. The variance and the standard deviation were found to be 0.0005 and 0.022 respectively.

Interference Studies: CN^- , SCN^- , S^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, citrate, tartrate and EDTA interfere. Alkali and alkaline earth metal ions, Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Ti^{4+} and Rh^{3+} , Ru^{3+} , do not interfere. V^{5+} , Mo^{6+} and W^{6+} are tolerated upto 15 ppm each for 4.0 ppm of Ni(II). Pd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} interfere strongly.

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Estimation of Allyl Alcohol, Crotyl Alcohol and Cinnamyl Alcohol with Chloramine-B

H. S. YATHIRAJAN, RANGASWAMY

and

D. S. MAHADEVAPPA

Department of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry,
Manasa Gangotri, Mysore-570006

Manuscript received 15 June 1978,

revised 25 October 1978; accepted 18 January 1979

CONJUGATED alcohols such as allyl, crotyl and cinnamyl alcohol have a number of important applications. Allyl alcohol finds a number of industrial applications in the preparation of resins, plasticisers, pharmaceuticals and many organic compounds. Crotyl alcohol finds use as a lachrymator, herbicide and soil fumigant, while cinnamyl alcohol is employed as a flavouring agent and in perfumery. Chloramine-B (CAB) has received considerable attention as a new oxidimetric reagent,¹⁻² and was first proposed by Afanas'ev.³ CAB is a stable compound with slightly higher active chlorine content⁴ than its analogue chloramine-T. During an investigation of the oxidation of alcohols by CAB, it was found that allyl, crotyl and cinnamyl alcohols undergo oxidation with a two electron change and substantial amounts of the alcohol can be estimated by a proper adjustment of reaction conditions. The present communication reports an elegant method for the estimation of allyl and crotyl alcohol in aqueous solution and cinnamyl alcohol in glacial acetic acid and ethanol-water (50 : 50 v/v) media, using CAB. Back titration procedures have been developed as the reaction was not instantaneous.

Experimental

Materials and Methods:

Allyl alcohol (Merck, corrected b.p. 97.1°, $n_D = 1.412$) and crotyl alcohol (Fluka, b.p. 125°, $n_D = 1.424$) were used without further purification. Cinnamyl alcohol (Naarden, corrected b.p. 256.6°) was distilled under reduced pressure. The purity of the compounds was checked by phthalation with phthalic anhydride in pyridine.⁵ The required quantity of (allyl and crotyl) alcohol was accurately weighed and dissolved in the proper solvent, while glacial acetic acid or ethanol-water (50 : 50 v/v) was used as solvents for cinnamyl alcohol. Chloramine-B was prepared⁶ by passing pure chlorine through benzene sulphonamide dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (4M) over a period of 1 hour at 70°. The mass obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from water. The purity of the compound was checked by estimating the amount of active chlorine present in the compound.⁷ An aqueous solution of CAB was prepared and standardised by the iodometric method. All other reagents were of accepted grades of purity. Standard buffer

systems were employed. Triply distilled water was used for preparing the solutions.

Preliminary Studies :

Known amount of allyl, crotyl and cinnamyl alcohol (~ 0.04 m. mole) in proper solvents were added to a known excessive volume of CAB (~ 0.8 m. mole) in an iodine flask. The reaction mixture was set aside at room temperature ($25 \pm 5^\circ$), for different intervals of time, with occasional shaking. Excess CAB present was then determined by back titration.

The extent of oxidation of allyl and crotyl alcohols by CAB in different buffer and solvent media was studied (CAB taken : 0.8 m. mole ; alcohol taken : 0.04 m. mole ; time : 5 min). Oxidation of the alcohols was sluggish in H_2SO_4 (0.1-0.5M) and $HClO_4$ (0.5M), but was stoichiometric with a two electron change in HCl medium (0.1-0.5M). It was noted that the reaction is slow in buffer medium (pH 1-7), the rate decreasing with the increase in pH. However, stoichiometric oxidation of the alcohols takes place in buffer of pH 1 in 10-15 minutes. Oxidation was non-stoichiometric in 0.1N NaOH medium.

The extent of oxidation of cinnamic alcohol by CAB in ethanol-water (50 : 50 v/v) and glacial acetic acid media has been investigated (CAB taken : 0.8 m. mole ; alcohol taken : 0.04 m. mole ; time : 5-60 min). Oxidation was almost instantaneous in ethanol-water medium and a two electron stoichiometry was obtained within 5 min. In glacial acetic acid, the required stoichiometry was attained after 45 min. However, the former method suffered from the following disadvantages :

1. During the estimation of unreacted CAB, small quantities of liberated iodine occlude on the reaction products and vigorous agitation of the reaction mixture was found necessary to obtain the true end point.

2. It was also found necessary to correct for a slight decomposition of oxidant brought about by ethanol, by including the same volume of ethanol-water mixture in the blank titration. Hence the estimation of cinnamyl alcohol by CAB was carried out in glacial acetic acid medium.

The rate of oxidation of cinnamyl alcohol is unaffected by the presence of hydrochloric acid or neutral salts. However, the presence of perchloric or sulphuric acid considerably retards the reaction, although the required stoichiometry could be attained after about 1 hour.

Recommended Procedure :

For Allyl and Crotyl Alcohols : Add aliquots of aqueous solution of allyl or crotyl alcohol solutions

($\sim 2-74$ mg) to an excess of CAB (~ 3 m. mole) containing enough 2M HCl to give an overall acid concentration (0.1-0.5M). After 5 min. add 10 ml of 2N H_2SO_4 , 20 ml of 10% KI and titrate against standard sodium thiosulphate solution.

For Cinnamyl Alcohol : Add aliquots of cinnamyl alcohol solution in glacial acetic acid ($\sim 2-64$ mg) to a measured excess of CAB (~ 3 m. mole) in an iodine flask and set aside for 45-50 min. with occasional shaking. Estimate the unconsumed CAB as in the case of allyl and crotyl alcohols.

Run a blank with CAB solution in both cases.

Results and Discussion

The 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the oxidation of alcohols can be represented as

The presence of allyl aldehyde⁸, crotyl aldehyde⁸ and cinnamyl aldehyde⁹ in the reaction products was shown by spot tests. Further the aldehydes were isolated as their 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone¹⁰ (m.p. 165°, 189° and 253° respectively for the hydrazones of allyl, crotyl and cinnamyl aldehydes). The presence of benzene sulphonamide among the reaction products was detected by TLC technique. A mixture of petroleum ether, chloroform and *n*-butanol (1 : 1 : 0.5 v/v) was used as the solvent with iodine as the developing reagent ($R_f = 0.88$).

Neutral salts have no influence on the rate of oxidation or stoichiometry, but the presence of perchloric or sulphuric acid considerably retards the reaction. The latter could probably be attributed to a combined specific inhibitory effect of H^+ , ClO_4^- and SO_4^{2-} ions. The stoichiometry is also unaffected by a reversal of the order of addition of the oxidant and alcohol.

During the present investigations, amounts of alcohols were varied between 2-75 mg and the error in recovery was less than $\pm 0.5\%$. By a proper adjustment of the reaction conditions, it is found possible to estimate substantial amounts of the conjugated alcohols by this method.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium with Pyrimidine-2-thiols

AJAI K. SINGH* and R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110007

Manuscript received 17 November 1977, revised 28 August 1978, accepted 8 September 1978

SEVERAL pyrimidine-2-thiols have been found to be promising chromogenic reagents for osmium and other platinum metals by Singh and coworkers¹⁻⁴. In continuation of these studies osmium-complexes of 1-propyl (I) – and 1-(6'-amino-5'-hydroxy-3'-mercaptopyrimidyl)-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H, 4H-pyrimidine-2-thiols (II) have been investigated spectrophotometrically. They are suitable for photometric determination of metal in micro-amounts. The results are reported in the present paper.

Experimental

Osmium(VIII) solution was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of OsO₄ (Johnson Mathey, England) in 0.2N sodium hydroxide. The solution was standardised iodometrically⁵. Pyrimidine-2-thiols were synthesised by the method of Mathes⁶. 0.01M solutions of these thiols were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of I in 0.02M hydrochloric acid and II in methanol. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade and doubly distilled water was used through out the studies. Unicam, SP-600, spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. Elico pH-meter, model LI-10, was used for pH measurements.

Procedure for Determination of Osmium with Thiol I :

To a suitable aliquot of solution containing 55 to 205 μg of osmium, add 1-2 ml of 5N hydrochloric acid and 4-5 ml of 0.01M solution of thiol I. Dilute the solution to 10 ml and set aside for 1 hr or heat for about 10 min. on a steam bath. Add 10 ml of *n*-butanol and shake for about 15 min. on an electric shaker. Separate organic layer, centrifuge and measure its absorbance at 510 nm against *n*-butanol blank. Deduce the osmium content from calibration curve.

Procedure for Determination of Osmium with Thiol II :

To osmium solution (containing 20-170 μg of metal), add 3-4 ml of 0.01M solution of thiol II in methanol and adjust pH of the solution in the range 4.5-8.0, using dilute solutions of hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide. Heat the solution for about 10 min. or keep aside for 45 min. Dilute it to 10 ml, keeping 50% methanolic medium (v/v). Measure the absorbance at 520 nm against 50% aqueous methanol blank and deduce metal content from precalibrated graph.

Results and Discussion

Osmium(VIII) reacts with colourless solutions of thiols I and II, in presence of dilute hydrochloric acid and in neutral or weakly acidic medium respectively. Reactions are slow at room temperature and take 1 hr. and 30 min. for completion with thiol I and II respectively. Alternatively 10 min. heating on a steam bath is also sufficient for full colour development with both the thiols. The complexes thus formed do not dissociate appreciably in 24 hr. The order of addition of various reagents does not affect the colour development in both cases. These thiols do not form coloured complexes on reaction with Os(IV), but a similar one with Os(VI). This indicates that in their osmium-complexes the oxidation state of metal is probably six and reduction with thiol takes place. Characteristics of osmium-complexes and optimum conditions for determination are as follows :

Osmium-1-propyl-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H,4H-pyrimidine-2-thiol (I) Complex :

Red coloured osmium-thiol I complex, having metal and ligand in 1 : 2 ratio, is extractable in several common organic solvents but the best results are obtained with *n*-butanol. Shaking for about 15 min. on an electric shaker is required for complete extraction. The complex absorbs maximum at 510 nm (ϵ 8200 l mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹). Full colour development takes place in the presence of 0.5-3.5N hydrochloric acid and 15-times molar excess of thiol. Sulphuric, nitric and perchloric acids are equally good for this purpose. The system obeys

* Presently at M. D. University, Rohtak.